

MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF ZANCHOR REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT LOADING

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Introduction

Zanchor process

Through-thickness reinforcement technique

Under static loading

Zanchor process can improve mode I and II fracture toughness. [1][2]

Under impact loading → Uncleared

Aim

To investigate the efficiency of Zanchor process for mode II fracture toughness **under impact loading.**

[1] T.Kusaka et al. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 96, 2012.

[2] T.Kusaka et al. *Composites Science and Technology*, 69, 2009.

Impact fracture toughness.

Mode II fracture toughness under impact loading can estimate using surface strain near crack tip.[3]

✘ Only initial crack growth.

→ **Could not estimate crack growth behavior**

SHPB system and ENF specimen

[3] T.Kusaka et al. *Key Engineering Materials*, 141-143, 1998.

Strain Distribution Transition analysis

SDT analysis was proposed to estimate crack growth behavior.

The validity was confirmed by FEM analysis.

Crack growth behavior under 10 m/s (FEM result)

Results and Conclusion

Crack growth resistance curves (R-curves)

Conclusion

The Zanchor process is improve mode II fracture toughness.

Efficiency of reinforcement with Zanchor process was higher under dynamic loading.

Fracture toughness of Zanchor composite depend on loading rate.